

Determination of the Principal Axes and Principal Moments of Inertia Using Euler Angles

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Abstract

Euler angles are used to determine the orientation of a set of axes relative to a base set of axes. Here, they are used to determine the principal axes of inertia, given the inertia tensor in a given base set of axes. The procedure determines the principal moments of inertia, as well. A diagonalization of the inertia tensor is, thus, performed without resort to the traditional eigen-value-problem approach.

Preliminaries

Let the inertia tensor be represented in the set of axes (x_0, y_0, z_0) by the inertia matrix

$$J_0 = \begin{bmatrix} A_0 & D_0 & E_0 \\ D_0 & B_0 & F_0 \\ E_0 & F_0 & G_0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We generate inertia matrices

$$J_1 = \begin{bmatrix} A_1 & D_1 & E_1 \\ D_1 & B_1 & F_1 \\ E_1 & F_1 & G_1 \end{bmatrix}, J_2 = \begin{bmatrix} A_2 & D_2 & E_2 \\ D_2 & B_2 & F_2 \\ E_2 & F_2 & G_2 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } J_3 = \begin{bmatrix} P & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Q & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R \end{bmatrix}$$

in the sets of axes (x_1, y_1, z_1) , (x_2, y_2, z_2) and (x_3, y_3, z_3) , through successive rotations of angles ϕ , θ and ψ around the axes $z_0 \equiv z_1$, $y_1 \equiv y_2$ and $z_2 \equiv z_3$, respectively, as depicted in Figs. 1.

Figs.1: Successive rotations through Euler angles ϕ , θ and ψ .

The corresponding successive transformation matrices

$$L_1 = \begin{bmatrix} c\phi & s\phi & 0 \\ -s\phi & c\phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad L_2 = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta & 0 & -s\theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ s\theta & 0 & c\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad L_3 = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi & s\psi & 0 \\ -s\psi & c\psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

have as transposes L_1' , L_2' and L_3' ; noting that, for brevity, c , s , and subsequently t stand for \cos , \sin and \tan .

Analysis

The backward evaluation of $J_2 = L_3' J_3 L_3$ gives

$$J_2 = \begin{bmatrix} Pc^2\psi + Qs^2\psi & (P - Q)s\psi c\psi & 0 \\ (P - Q)s\psi c\psi & Ps^2\psi + Qc^2\psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R \end{bmatrix}$$

Comparison of the two above-given expressions for J_2 results in

$A_2 = Pc^2\psi + Qs^2\psi$	(1A)
$B_2 = Ps^2\psi + Qc^2\psi$	(1B)
$G_2 = R$	(1G)
$D_2 = (P - Q)s\psi c\psi$	(1D)
$E_2 = 0$	(1E)
$F_2 = 0$	(1F)

The forward evaluation of $J_2 = L_2 L_1 J_0 L_1' L_2'$ and rearrangement give

$A_2 = (A_0 c^2 \phi + B_0 s^2 \phi + 2D_0 s \phi c \phi - G_0) c^2 \theta - 2(E_0 c \phi + F_0 s \phi) s \theta c \theta + G_0$	(2A)
$B_2 = A_0 s^2 \phi + B_0 c^2 \phi - 2D_0 s \phi c \phi$	(2B)
$G_2 = (A_0 c^2 \phi + B_0 s^2 \phi + 2D_0 s \phi c \phi - G_0) s^2 \theta + 2(E_0 c \phi + F_0 s \phi) s \theta c \theta + G_0$	(2G)
$D_2 = [(B_0 - A_0) s \phi c \phi + D_0 (c^2 \phi - s^2 \phi)] c \theta + (E_0 s \phi - F_0 c \phi) s \theta$	(2D)
$E_2 = (A_0 c^2 \phi + B_0 s^2 \phi + 2D_0 s \phi c \phi - G_0) s \theta c \theta + (E_0 c \phi + F_0 s \phi) (c^2 \theta - s^2 \theta)$	(2E)
$F_2 = [(B_0 - A_0) s \phi c \phi + D_0 (c^2 \phi - s^2 \phi)] s \theta - (E_0 s \phi - F_0 c \phi) c \theta$	(2F)

Equations (1E) and (2E) give

$(A_0 c^2 \phi + B_0 s^2 \phi + 2D_0 s \phi c \phi - G_0) s \theta c \theta + (E_0 c \phi + F_0 s \phi) (c^2 \theta - s^2 \theta) = 0$	(3a)
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while Eqs. (1F) and (2F) give

$[(B_0 - A_0) s \phi c \phi + D_0 (c^2 \phi - s^2 \phi)] s \theta - (E_0 s \phi - F_0 c \phi) c \theta = 0$	(3b)
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Equations (3a) and (3b) are two equations for ϕ and θ that can be solved either by bisection or iteratively by Newton-Raphson method. Substitution in Eqs. (2A), (2B), (2D) and (2G) determines A_2 , B_2 , D_2 and G_2 .

An interesting result follows from the expression for R , obtained from Eqs. (1G) and (2G),

$R = (A_0 c^2 \phi + B_0 s^2 \phi + 2D_0 s \phi c \phi - G_0) s^2 \theta + 2(E_0 c \phi + F_0 s \phi) s \theta c \theta + G_0$	(3c)
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which differentiates to

$$R_\theta = 2\{(A_0 c^2 \phi + B_0 s^2 \phi + 2D_0 s \phi c \phi - G_0) s \theta c \theta + (E_0 c \phi + F_0 s \phi) (c^2 \theta - s^2 \theta)\}$$

$$R_\phi = 2\{[(B_0 - A_0) s \phi c \phi + D_0 (c^2 \phi - s^2 \phi)] s \theta - (E_0 s \phi - F_0 c \phi) c \theta\} s \theta$$

so that, upon use of (3a) and (3b), we get $R_\theta = 0$ and $R_\phi = 0$, showing that R is extremum with respect to variations in ϕ and θ .

To get ψ , P and Q , we manipulate Eqs. (1A), (1B) and (1D) to get

$t(2\psi) = 2D_2/(A_2 - B_2)$	(3d)
$P = A_2c^2\psi + B_2s^2\psi + 2D_2s\psi c\psi$	(3e)
$Q = A_2s^2\psi + B_2c^2\psi - 2D_2s\psi c\psi$	(3f)

The principal axes of inertia x_3 , y_3 and z_3 have direction cosines, relative to the (x_0, y_0, z_0) axes, that are given by the elements of the rows of the matrix $L_3L_2L_1$. They are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Direction cosines of the principal axes of inertia.

Axis	Direction cosines		
	with x_0	with y_0	with z_0
x_3	$c\psi c\theta c\phi - s\psi s\phi$	$c\psi c\theta s\phi + s\psi c\phi$	$-c\psi s\theta$
y_3	$-s\psi c\theta c\phi - c\psi s\phi$	$-s\psi c\theta s\phi + c\psi c\phi$	$s\psi s\theta$
z_3	$s\theta c\phi$	$s\theta s\phi$	$c\theta$

Concluding remark

For a given inertia tensor, the set of principal axes of inertia are unique. However, they can be ordered in different ways and can be assigned different senses. Therefore, the set of Euler angles describing these principal axes is not unique.

As an example, the inertia tensor with matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} 9 & -4 & -3 \\ -4 & 8 & -2 \\ -3 & -2 & 7 \end{bmatrix}$$

in the axes (x_0, y_0, z_0) is diagonalized by three different sets of Euler angles, as illustrated in Tables 2.

Tables 2: Non-uniqueness of Euler angles for principal axes of inertia.

(a)

Axis	Direction cosines			Principal moments of inertia
	with x_0	with y_0	with z_0	
x_3	0.211324865405187	0.577350269189626	-0.788675134594813	9.267949192431121
y_3	-0.788675134594813	0.577350269189626	0.211324865405187	12.732050807568877
z_3	0.577350269189626	0.577350269189626	0.577350269189626	2
Euler angles	ϕ	θ	ψ	in degrees
	45	54.735610317245346	15	

(b)

Axis	Direction cosines			Principal moment of inertia
	with x_0	with y_0	with z_0	
x_3	0.577350269189626	0.577350269189626	0.577350269189626	2
y_3	0.788675134594813	-0.577350269189626	-0.211324865405187	12.732050807568877
z_3	0.211324865405187	0.577350269189626	-0.788675134594813	9.267949192431121
Euler angles	ϕ	θ	ψ	in degrees
	-110.10390936101710	-142.06187257281451	20.103909361017095	

(c)

Axis	Direction cosines			Principal moment of inertia
	with x_0	with y_0	with z_0	
x_3	-0.577350269189626	-0.577350269189626	-0.577350269189626	2
y_3	-0.788675134594813	0.577350269189626	0.211324865405187	12.732050807568877
z_3	0.211324865405187	0.577350269189626	-0.788675134594813	9.267949192431121
Euler angles	ϕ	θ	ψ	in degrees
	69.896090638982912	142.061872572814508	20.103909361017106	